

CONTENT-BASED ACCESS TO MULTIMEDIA EDUCATIONAL LIBRARIES

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ABSTRACT

The availability of huge amounts of digital multimedia information introduces new challenges for the efficient representation of the data and the access to it. This document describes a system designed to allow such an access for a concrete type of information (educational video material) with a defined architecture (a client-server model over standard IP networks).

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper describes a system designed to provide broadband services applied to the deployment of digital video libraries oriented to educational environments. The objective is to create a platform that supports applications focused to ease distance learning by the creation of multimedia courses, stored in servers and accessed by client platforms through heterogeneous networks. Such applications already exist in the market; the goal is to enhance the accessibility of the content by incorporating emerging technologies in the field of content representation [1]. To that purpose, the content is indexed by using meta-information suitable for later content-based browsing and retrieval, in the style of the future MPEG-7 standard [2].

Systems with capabilities like the ones described in this paper are deemed to achieve an increasing importance due to the foreseeable on-line availability of vast amounts of multimedia content. The work currently undergoing in standardization bodies (like the mentioned ISO/MPEG) will make possible the necessary interoperability among systems.

We begin this paper by describing the system architecture and the way the video content is processed, then proceed to give an overview of some details on the description scheme used for meta-information, and finally comment the procedure used by the client to access and recover the content.

2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND PROCESSING OF CONTENT

In this section we explain the procedure needed to install new content on the server, making it ready for searching,

navigation and access. We will focus on video content (since it is the most demanding in terms of processing), but the system allows the storage of image presentations (e.g. slide shows) as well. The audiovisual material follows a series of steps to achieve its final storage on the server:

- Digitizing and encoding. We are assuming that the original material is present in traditional form (video tapes), coming from course production, and classroom or conference recordings. Thus, the first step carried out is its conversion into a digital encoded stream. We have chosen MPEG-1 as encoding format due to its good quality and availability of software decoders for the most popular client platforms. However the system accepts also MPEG-2 (if higher quality is desired and the needed bandwidth is available) and MPEG-4 frame-based video (used at lower bitrates for more limited networks).
- Storage on the video server. The encoded audiovisual material is transferred to a streaming video server system, capable of delivering the content to clients through standard IP networks (TCP/IP for control and UDP/IP for video transport).
- Automatic preanalysis. In parallel with the storage in the video server, the content goes through an automatic cataloguing system. Several techniques [3, 4, 5, 6] are used to perform such tasks as
 - temporal segmentation (cut detection),
 - keyframe extraction,
 - video motion classification, and
 - image analysis through low-level (texture and color) description algorithms over selected image areas.

This information is transformed into a basic temporal decomposition of the video and a set of binary (*low-level*) meta-data for the video segments. These are stored in a specialized descriptor server, designed to perform efficient queries on this kind of low-level information.

Figure 1: System architecture

- Instructor annotation. Once the content has been preanalyzed, human intervention is needed to correct possible errors from the automatic phase and provide higher level meta-information. To this purpose a cataloguing terminal has been designed which allows:

- Structuring the segments into semantically meaningful clusters, by means of a tree-based user interface. This permits the creation of an hierarchical representation for each video document, subdivided into units such as topics or scenes (see section 3 for details).

We are currently developing algorithms to aid the teacher/cataloguer in this semantic grouping by using the low-level properties to suggest an initial grouping.

- Adding high level meta-information, by filling descriptive fields such as author, subject, title, etc. A modified subset (adapted to video material) of the Dublin Core description set [7] is used for this purpose.

Note that, while the system allows insertion of rights-holder information (such as owner or copyright), it will never claim to be authoritative on this topic; there are a number of very sensitive issues related to intellectual property management which are outside the scope of this work.

All high-level meta-information, as well as the description of the resulting video structure, is stored in a standard Relational Database System, which acts as a core to link the high-level descriptions, the low-level meta-

information and the actual content stored in the video server. The client interaction with the database works through a WWW gateway.

Figure 1 shows a general diagram of the system with the main building blocks, as well as the path followed by the information.

3 DATA MODEL

Figure 2 shows the hierarchy used for the video content. The highest self-contained unit is called a *video document*, and it is subdivided into a tree of smaller elements. The subdivision may be semantic (*topics*), semantic/syntactic (*scenes*) or merely syntactic (*shots*, *images*).

Figure 2: Video hierarchy

The lowest unit (*object*) represents any entity (semantic or syntactic) present in the video frame. In principle it allows arbitrarily sized objects within the image frame, although for practical purposes (due to the amount of effort needed to create accurate segmentation of semantic objects) we are currently using rectangular-shaped regions.

Video documents can also be grouped (by subjects or any other criteria) to form *collections*, which may also be nested to create collection trees. In this way subsets of the global video library may be established to ease the content navigation.

Each of the hierarchy units in which a video document is decomposed can have meta-information assigned to

them. Following MPEG-7 terminology [8] we will call the basic meta-information unit a *descriptor*. In its simplest form it is nothing more than an (*attribute, value*) couple.

Together all the descriptors for all the data units of a content form the *description* of that content.

A model of data inheritance is established on the video units, so that descriptors can be inherited both downwards and upwards in the hierarchy. There are therefore two main procedures for data propagation:

- **Simple inheritance:** These descriptors can have only one value at each time (i.e., for each data unit). By default their values propagate downward to the sublevels of each unit, but at each data level they can be overloaded with a different value. These descriptors are, therefore, exclusive.

An example of a descriptor with this propagation is *Subject*. It is usually assigned to an entire video document (e.g. a news program has a subject of *news*), and then that value is inherited by its sublevels. However it is possible to overload the propagated value at a given sublevel, e.g. a shot within a news program may correspond to a report from a football match, and for that shot the descriptor value is *sports* (which would allow locating a sports shot even inside a news program).

- **Aggregated inheritance:** this is used for descriptors which can present multiple values. This type of descriptors is typically assigned to the smaller data units (e.g. *image, shot*), and they propagate upwards by aggregating all the values that are present in the lower branches. They can be considered set descriptors, in the sense that the order of the components in the descriptor value is not important, just their presence, and for a set each component has a maximum cardinality of one.

An example may be a descriptor for *Person*, which allows searching for the presence of identified people in the data units. The values for a shot would contain all the persons present in that shot; values for bigger data units would aggregate all the components in their sublevels. Note that for a given video level this aggregation allows the detection of the simultaneous presence (i.e. in the *same* temporal period) of more than one component of the descriptor value only with the temporal resolution of the level.

This propagation system is mostly designed for search purposes. Since it is mainly an static procedure, it can be pre-computed and stored in the database. Doing it at the creation (or update) phase allows for more efficiency, at the expense of increased storage space needed and some loss of flexibility.

Additionally there can be also local descriptors, for which there is no inheritance defined across the hierarchy. Low-level descriptors are currently treated this way, so that they are not propagated through the hierarchy.

4 CLIENT OPERATION

The client application allows browsing and searching, and visualizing AV content:

- a) The client includes a content browser which allows navigation through the data units stored in the server in a tree-like fashion; it is also possible to arbitrarily hide and show details of the hierarchy. Short summaries of the videos (as still-image slide shows) are also available for fast inspection.
- b) For search operations the user must indicate both the descriptors he/she is looking for, and the level in the data hierarchy for which results are wanted.

Currently only one hierarchy level is allowed to be selected for search purposes, so that the user must know in advance the level of detail he/she desires to obtain from the search operation. This shortcoming will be addressed in future versions.

The system will return a list of data units with matching descriptors; they will be placed onto the browse tree so that it is possible to navigate upwards or downwards from them.

This means that there is a double possibility of starting an interaction with the system:

- It can begin with a top-down navigation across the structure (general browsing), until an element of interest is shown. This is equivalent to the *table of contents* paradigm.
- Or it can start by performing a search for a subelement, when some specific details are known. This corresponds to the *index* paradigm.

4.1 Using low-level descriptors

Low-level descriptors can also be employed for search purposes, by performing a query-by-example type of search. However this implies that this kind of descriptors cannot be used in the first step of a search. Instead they may form the basis for the second stage of a multi-stage localization operation, either navigation-started or search-started (with a high-level search):

$$\begin{array}{l} \textit{navigation} \rightarrow \textit{low level} \rightarrow \textit{retrieval} \\ \textit{search} \\ \textit{high level} \rightarrow \textit{low level} \rightarrow \textit{retrieval} \\ \textit{search} \quad \quad \quad \textit{search} \end{array}$$

Of course after the low-level search the procedure may be restarted. Low- and high-level searches may also be combined to further restrict the result set.

Figure 3: Client application

4.2 User Terminal

In order to allow a multi-platform execution, the browse and search client application has been developed in Java. This application shows the video tree, information about descriptors and images and video summaries of the content, and also provides the search interface through a collection of menus.

Once a content element has been selected for playback, the information needed to access the component is fed into a media player, which then accesses the server and presents the desired video unit (the system allows presentation of only a selected subunit, as well as entire video documents).

Figure 3 shows two screen shots from the terminal application: the content browser with a video tree and one search window for a class of descriptors.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have described the architecture and operation of a system built to provide content-based access capabilities to video libraries. Although the system has been designed for a certain class of content (educational video documents), it could be used with other types, since most meta-information is dynamically defined in a database, which allows readaptation as needed.

This flexibility will also allow alignment with future international standards such as MPEG-7, a requirement to achieve interoperability with other systems.

The system has also been planned as a testbed for algorithms for content-based access and organization of video information. As such, it is expected to evolve over time, through the incorporation of new functionalities and the subsequent feedback from end users.

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